

Effectiveness of Collaborating Strategies in Enhancing the Reading Level of Junior High School Learners in Lopez West District, Division of Quezon

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Abstract. This study determined the effectiveness of collaborating strategies in enhancing the reading level of Junior High School learners in Lopez West District, Division of Quezon. The primary objectives were to determine the learner's reading level before and after the implementation of collaborating strategies, identify if there is a significant difference between the results, identify the challenges and actions taken by Junior High School teachers. Utilizing descriptive and quasi-experimental designs, data were gathered from 17 Junior High School teachers and 75 Grade 7 learners of Jongo National High School using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory. The data were analyzed using statistical tools, including mean scores and paired sample t-test. The developed and implemented collaborating strategies was a reading process based on the term COLLABOREAD. Findings revealed that pre-assessment results indicated that Grade 7 learners fell in the frustration level and instructional level. After collaborating, post-assessment results showed significant improvement among learners in both classes. Statistical analysis confirmed the significant difference on learner's reading level before and after the implementation of collaborating strategies. Teachers faced challenges such as classroom management, learners' motivation, and time required for collaborative activities. To address the issues, teachers used visual aids, interactive activities, peer-buddy support, and monitored reading progress. Based on these findings, Collaborating Framework was proposed to help teachers and learners to enhance their reading level, particularly in reading comprehension. The study concluded that collaborating effectively enhances their understanding of texts, developing critical thinking and encouraging active participation in reading activities. It is recommended that teachers integrate diverse tools and strategies to address different learning needs.

Introduction

Reading is one of the fundamental macro skills that serves as a cornerstone for learning and academic achievement. It functions as a primary tool for acquiring knowledge and developing critical thinking. Strong reading skills enable learners to access information, construct meaning from texts, and participate effectively in academic discourse. As an essential component of literacy, reading empowers learners to overcome ignorance and misinformation, thereby contributing significantly to their overall educational development.

Despite the importance of reading, many high school learners continue to experience serious difficulties in reading comprehension, particularly in English. Reading challenges among secondary learners remain a persistent concern in the Philippine educational system. According to the World Bank's learning poverty data, a large proportion of Filipino children struggle to read and understand simple texts by age 10. Moreover, results from the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) show that Filipino learners demonstrate low reading proficiency compared with their international counterparts. National reports further indicate that a substantial number of senior high school graduates are unable to read or comprehend basic materials, highlighting an urgent need for effective reading interventions (Bordey, 2025).

At the local level, the Lopez West District in the Division of Quezon, Philippines, has also identified significant concerns regarding reading comprehension among junior high school learners. District reports reveal persistent literacy challenges based on the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) results. For School Year 2024–2025, an average of 33.94% of the 4,743 junior high school learners were classified as instructional, frustration, or non-readers in the post-assessment. These data indicate that a considerable number of learners remain at the lowest reading levels and require targeted instructional support.

Previous studies emphasize that the quality of instruction, teaching approaches, and language development significantly influence learners' learning outcomes. Churchward and Willis (2023) noted that effective pedagogy and meaningful lessons contribute to the improvement of learners' language skills. Reading strategies, in particular, play an essential role in helping learners become proficient readers. Exposure to varied strategies enhances learners' comprehension and engagement with texts. Collaborative learning involves learners actively working together toward common goals, emphasizing meaningful interaction rather than simply completing group tasks. This cooperative engagement enhances understanding of the material and peer involvement, leading to improved learning outcomes for the whole class (Athuraliya, 2026).

Based on the researcher's classroom observations, traditional teaching methods appear to have limited effectiveness in addressing the needs of non-readers and frustration-level learners. These approaches often emphasize rote memorization and passive learning, which do not actively engage learners or develop higher-order thinking skills. As a result, many learners remain disengaged and struggle to form meaningful connections with reading materials, leading to weak performance in comprehension tasks.

Collaboreading refers to a structured reading process that promote interaction among learners as they engage with texts. Through shared reading, discussion, questioning, and peer support, learners are encouraged to construct meaning collectively. Integrating collaboreading strategies in the classroom may create a more dynamic learning environment where learners actively participate, exchange insights, and support one another in overcoming reading difficulties.

In this context, the present study focuses on the use of collaboreading strategies in enhancing the reading levels of junior high school learners. Specifically, it aims to determine the effectiveness of collaboreading strategies in enhancing the reading level of Junior High School learners. Ultimately, the study seeks to contribute practical reading interventions that respond not only to local classroom needs but also to the broader challenges faced by Filipino learners in reading comprehension.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to determine the effectiveness of collaboreading strategies in enhancing the reading level of Junior High School learners in Lopez West District, Division of Quezon. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the reading level of Junior High School learners before the use of collaboreading strategies based on Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) pre-assessment tool?
2. What is the reading level of Junior High School learners after the use of collaboreading strategies based on Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) post-assessment tool?
3. Is there a significant difference on the reading level of Junior High School learners based on the results of Phil-IRI pre- and post-assessment using collaboreading strategies?
4. What are the challenges encountered by Junior High School teachers using collaborative reading strategies in terms of:
 - 5.1 pre-implementation;
 - 5.2 during implementation; and
 - 5.3 post-implementation?
5. What actions have been implemented by Junior High School teachers to address the challenges in their classrooms in terms of:

- 5.1 pre-implementation;
- 5.2 during implementation; and
- 5.3 post-implementation?

6. What framework could be proposed by the researcher to effectively implement the collaboreading strategies based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed mixed-methods research design, integrating both descriptive and quasi-experimental approaches. The descriptive component utilizes a survey questionnaire to identify the challenges encountered by Junior High School teachers, and the actions taken to address those challenges. As defined by Best and Kahn (2006), descriptive research is “concerned with conditions or relationships that exist; practices that prevail; beliefs, points of view, or attitudes that are held; processes that are going on; effects that are being felt; or trends that are developing.” Similarly, recent literature explains that descriptive research aims to systematically describe a population or phenomenon by identifying existing conditions, characteristics, and trends (McCombes, 2023).

On the other hand, the quasi-experimental design employed collaboreading strategies using the collaboreading framework, which is a process used by the researcher in conducting collaboreading strategies for experimentation. This involved the use of pre- and post-assessment data from the Phil-IRI to measure the reading level of learners before and after using collaboreading. Creswell (2014) defined quasi-experimental research as “experimental situations in which the researcher assigns treatments but cannot randomly assign participants to groups.” Similarly, recent literature explains that quasi-experimental designs involve the manipulation of variables without random assignment of participants, distinguishing them from true experimental designs (Thomas, 2024).

This study used this method to determine the effectiveness of collaboreading strategies in enhancing the reading level of Junior High School learners in Lopez West District. Likewise, this method will allow for the triangulation of data, where findings from different methods are compared and corroborated, strengthening the validity and reliability of the research.

Thus, the study began with a survey questionnaire to generate generalizable results. Teachers' responses were collected using a 4-point Likert scale, providing significant perceptions into the challenges encountered by Junior High School teachers, and the actions they took to address the challenges before, during, and after implementation. Afterwards, two sections of Grade 7 took pre-assessment before the intervention and post-assessment after the intervention period. Collaboreading strategies was implemented in the classroom using a structured reading process based on the word COLLABOREAD, which stands for Connect, Organize Roles, Learn Together, Link Ideas, Analyze, Build Meaning, Offer Insights, Reflect, Extend Learning, Assess Understanding, and Document Learning, and it was divided into three reading stages, which are Pre-reading, During Reading and Post-reading. The differences between the results of pre-assessment and post-assessment were analyzed to determine the effectiveness of collaboreading strategies. The study was conducted for two weeks from October 1-17 of School Year 2025-2026 during the regular schedule of English classes in Jongo National High School.

Respondents/Participants

This study included 75 Grade 7 learners and 17 English teachers from public secondary schools in Lopez West District. The researcher employed purposive sampling to select English teachers from secondary schools. In this approach, the researcher exercises judgment to identify a sample that best aligns with the study's objectives (Mweshi & Sakyi, 2020). The selected English teachers responded to a survey questionnaire.

Meanwhile, the researcher used Jongo National High School in the Lopez West District to implement collaboreading strategies in an experimental study in Grade 7 classes. This school was chosen because it met the general characteristics required for the study, particularly in terms of learners experiencing reading comprehension difficulties, making it an appropriate setting for the implementation of collaboreading strategies.

Instrument of the Study

The researcher used a survey questionnaire on the challenges encountered by Junior High School teachers and the action taken to address the challenges for pre-implementation, during implementation, and post-implementation, respectively. The data was gathered from Junior High School teachers teaching the English subject. Some of the indicators in this study were derived from other sources, while the others were developed by the researcher. The field expert validated the instrument to ensure its reliability.

Cronbach's alpha was utilized to calculate the internal consistency of the questionnaires. The results indicated excellent reliability for the challenges encountered by Junior High School using collaborative reading strategies, with coefficients of 0.9290154. Meanwhile, the action taken to address the challenges using collaborative reading strategies demonstrated very good reliability, with a coefficient of 0.86707867. These results prove that the survey questionnaires have excellent to very good reliability. The researcher used the Group Screening Tool (GST) for pre-assessment and post-assessment, and the reading passages for collaborereading implementation from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) manual of 2018.

The gathering was divided into two sections. The first section is a survey questionnaire on the challenges encountered by Junior High School teachers using collaborative reading strategies, and the actions taken to address the challenges for pre-implementation, during implementation, and post-implementation. The last section is the implementation of the collaborereading strategies among the Grade 7 learners in the identified school. The collaborereading strategies is a process during reading sessions in which the researcher used three reading stages: Pre-reading, During Reading, and Post-reading. During the stages, the researcher used a sequence of processes from the COLLABOREAD, which stands for Connect, Organize Roles, Learn Together, Link Ideas, Analyze, Build Meaning, Offer Insights, Reflect, Extend Learning, Assess Understanding, and Document Learning, indicating the flow of the collaborereading session.

Procedure

The questionnaire used a 4-point Likert scale to determine the effectiveness of collaborereading strategies in enhancing the reading level of Junior High School learners. The research instruments were reviewed and validated by education experts, including master teachers and a teacher with a doctoral degree. Any necessary modifications were made based on their feedback and suggestions.

A letter requesting permission to conduct the study was first submitted to the Schools Division Office for the Schools Division Superintendent's signature, along with the attached research instrument and Data Sharing Agreement. Once the office released the 1st Endorsement, the researcher submitted a letter addressed to the Public Schools District Supervisor to the Lopez West District Office. Once approval was granted, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaire via Google Forms to the English teachers, and others received a hard copy. Participants were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire.

Afterwards, the researcher also submitted a letter to the school head of Jonggo National High School regarding the implementation of collaborereading strategies among the Grade 7 learners. Once approval was granted, the researcher conducted an orientation and obtained informed consent. During the orientation, the researcher explained the purpose of the study and assured them that their participation was voluntary, confidential, and for academic purposes only. Next, a pre-assessment was conducted before the implementation of collaborereading using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) tool, and the same assessment was used for post-assessment. The researcher took 2 weeks for the implementation of collaborereading for both sections of Grade 7 using the reading passage adapted in the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). During the implementation of collaborereading, the researcher applied the developed sequence of processes based on the word COLLABOREAD, which stands for Connect, Organize Roles, Learn Together, Link Ideas, Analyze, Build Meaning, Offer Insights, Reflect, Extend Learning, Assess Understanding, and Document Learning. Afterwards, the researcher conducted a post-assessment using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). The results of pre-assessment and post-assessment before and after the implementation of collaborereading strategies were tabulated and statistically analyzed using the mean, standard deviation, and paired sample t-test to determine the effectiveness of collaborereading strategies. The researcher ensured each participant's identity was kept highly confidential to maintain ethical standards in conducting this study.

Data Analysis

The statistical treatment of data for this study involved several steps to determine the effectiveness of collaboreading strategies in enhancing the reading level of Grade 7 learners.

In Statement of the Problem No. 1, the reading level of Junior High School learners before collaboreading strategies is assessed using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) pre-assessment.

In Statement of the Problem No. 2, the reading level of Junior High School learners after collaboreading strategies is assessed using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) post-assessment tool.

Both Statement of the Problem No. 1 and No. 2 used frequency distributions, percentage, mean, and standard deviations.

In Statement of the Problem No. 3, the researcher used the paired-sample t-test to compare two related groups and assess the effectiveness of collaboreading strategies in class in enhancing learners' reading level.

In Statement of Problem No. 4 and No. 5, the researcher identified the challenges encountered by Junior High School teachers using collaborative reading strategies and the actions taken to address the challenges, respectively. To achieve this, a 4-point Likert-scale questionnaire was used to collect responses from participants. The collected data were analyzed using the weighted mean to determine the extent and variability of the challenges encountered and the actions taken by teachers when using collaborative reading strategies.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were followed by the Junior High School teachers teaching English and Grade 7 learners in conducting the study. The research proposal was submitted to the Research Ethics Committee of Marinduque State University for ethical review. The following rights of the participants were considered:

1. Voluntary participation of participants is ensured. Their participation in the data-gathering procedure was completely voluntary. The teacher-participants may withdraw at any time or skip any question if they are uncomfortable. Meanwhile, the identified learner participants may decline to participate in the experimental process.
2. There were no known risks experienced by the participants in the conduct of the data gathering.
3. Confidentiality of information was observed during the conduct of the study, such as identifying information about the learners.
4. Informed consent was taken from English teachers and Grade 7 learners after the letter of request for the data collection was approved by the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent. Participants are fully informed about the procedures that were utilized. Their consent to participate was secured. Informed consent was included with the research instrument, and prior to answering the instrument, participants were instructed to read the consent form and sign it.
5. Further, unethical activities were not done in this study, especially the failure to acknowledge the contributions of other people in the field.

Results and Discussion

Reading Level	Grade 7 – Ilang-ilang (Pre-Assessment)		Grade 7 – Sampaguita (Pre-Assessment)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Frustration	30	76.90	19	52.80
Instructional	9	23.10	17	47.20
Independent	0	0	0	0
Total	39	100	36	100
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
	1.23	0.43	1.47	0.51

Table 1. Reading Level of Junior High School Learners Before Using Collaborereading Strategies Based on the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI)

The table 1 shows the distribution of 36 Grade 7–Sampaguita learners by pre-assessment reading level. Most of the students, 19 out of 36 (52.80%), fall under the Frustration Level, while 17 students (47.20%) are in the instructional level. Notably, no learner (0%) reached the independent level. The computed mean of 1.47, with a standard deviation of 0.51, indicates that most scores cluster toward the lower reading categories, with minimal variation among learners.

For Grade 7–Ilang-ilang, the pre-assessment involved 39 learners. The data reveal that 30 students (76.90%) are at the frustration level, while only 9 students (23.10%) fall under the Instructional Level. Similar to Sampaguita, no learner (0%) achieved the independent level. The weighted mean of 1.23 and standard deviation of 0.43 indicate an even stronger concentration of learners in the lowest reading category, with slightly less variability compared to Sampaguita.

The results indicate that Grade 7–Sampaguita's overall reading proficiency before the intervention was below the expected reading standard. Notably, no learner in the section was classified as an independent reader based on the Phil-IRI results before the implementation of the Collaborereading Strategies. Similarly, Grade 7–Ilang-ilang shows a greater concern with critical reading proficiency than Sampaguita, as a significantly larger proportion of learners fell below the frustration level, and none were identified as independent readers.

The recent findings were similar to the study of Cabural and Infantado (2023), which highlighted that learners, particularly grade 10 learners, exhibit low reading comprehension skills. Even on easy-level comprehension tasks, these learners struggle, finding literal and reorganizational comprehension moderately difficult, while inferential and evaluative tasks pose even greater challenges. This indicates a pressing need for students to enhance their ability to grasp both direct and implied information within texts.

Roque et al. (2023) found that pupils in lower grades, specifically Grades 1 and 2, have difficulty reading, as most fall into the non-reader and frustration levels. The school must therefore devise a reading program for early primary-grade pupils to ensure early development of reading skills. In line with these findings, Misanes and Pascual (2023) reported that 98.7% of the respondents in their study were classified at the frustration level—the lowest reading category—indicating that the materials were too difficult for the learners to comprehend and respond to effectively.

Reading Level	Grade 7 - Ilang-ilang (Post-Assessment)		Grade 7 - Sampaguita (Post-Assessment)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Frustration	19	48.70	16	44.40
Instructional	16	41.00	15	41.70
Independent	4	10.30	5	13.90
Total	39	100	36	100
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
	1.62	0.67	1.69	0.71

Table 2. Reading Level of Junior High School Learners After Using Collaborereading Strategies Based on the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI)

The post-assessment results for Grade 7–Ilang-ilang include 39 learners. Of this number, 19 learners (48.70%) remain at the Frustration Level, 16 learners (41.00%) have progressed to the Instructional Level, and 4 learners (10.30%) have reached the Independent Level. Compared with the pre-assessment, when no learners were independent, the emergence of independent readers signifies improvement. For Grade 7–Sampaguita, the post-assessment covered 36 learners. The results show 16 learners (44.40%) at the Frustration Level, 15 learners (41.70%) at the instructional level, and 5 learners (13.90%) at the independent level. Compared with the pre-assessment, when no learner was independent, this indicates measurable progress in reading level.

The results reveal a significant improvement in learners' reading proficiency following the implementation of Collaborereading Strategies. In Grade 7–Ilang-ilang, the number of learners at the frustration level dropped from 30 to 19. It shows that 11 learners left due to frustration. At the same time, the number in the instructional level increased from 9 to

16, while 4 learners progressed to the independent level. Similarly, Grade 7–Sampaguita shows positive progress: learners at the frustration level decreased from 19 to 16, while those at the instructional level decreased slightly from 17 to 15. Five (5) learners reached independent from an initial count of zero before the intervention.

In support of these findings, Caabay, Martinez, Valdestamon, and Aguhayon (2024) reported that targeted reading interventions for Grade 7 learners—incorporating strategies such as background knowledge activation, repeated readings, reading aloud, and guided questioning—led to a significant decrease in the number of learners at the frustration level, while increasing the proportion of learners at the instructional and independent reading levels.

Both sections show clear progress from pre- to post-assessment, particularly with the emergence of independent readers and increased mean scores. While improvements are evident, a significant portion of learners remains at the frustration level, indicating that the intervention was effective but should be continued and strengthened to achieve higher levels of reading independence across both classes.

Grade 7 – Ilang-ilang					Grade 7 – Sampaguita				
Pre-Assessment Mean	Post-Assessment Mean	Mean Difference	P-value	Decision	Pre Assessment Mean	Post Assessment Mean	Mean Difference	P-value	Decision
5.64	7.61	-1.97436	<0.001	With a significant difference	7.17	8.75	-1.58333	0.022	With a significant difference

Table 3. *Significant Difference on the Reading Level of Junior High School Learners Using Collaborating Strategies Based on the Results of Phil-IRI pre and post-assessment*

Table 3 reveals that both Grade 7 sections showed statistically significant improvements in reading level after implementing the collaborading strategies. The p-values for both sections ($p < 0.001$ for Ilang-Ilang and $p = 0.022$ for Sampaguita) are below the conventional significance threshold of 0.05, indicating that the improvements are unlikely due to chance

The null hypothesis is rejected for both sections. There are significant differences on the reading level of Junior High School learners based on the result of Phil-IRI pre-assessment and post-assessment in both sections. The findings suggest that the strategy effectively enhanced reading comprehension and engagement among the learners.

	Indicators	Weighted Mean (WM)	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
Pre-implementation			
1	I struggle with the availability of reading materials for collaborative reading activities which require them for additional preparation or resources.	2.88	UE
2	I consume a lot of time crafting collaborading activities, especially when considering the appropriate activities for different reading abilities of the students.	3.00	UE
3	I have a lack of professional training in addressing struggling readers in class.	1.94	SE
4	I have difficulty in aligning collaborative reading strategies within the current curriculum and lesson plans.	1.94	SE
5	I struggle to encourage students who have low reading ability to participate in collaborative reading.	2.12	SE
Composite Mean		2.37	SE

During Implementation		
6	I struggle to implement collaborative reading in their class because some students, particularly those at the frustration and instructional reading levels, are less engaged and lack interest.	2.23 SE
7	I find it challenging to implement collaborative reading strategies because the time allotment for one subject is insufficient.	2.76 UE
8	I unable to effectively implement collaborative reading due to large class sizes, which are hard to manage during group tasks.	2.53 UE
9	I encounter classroom management issue such as noise, and off-task behavior during collaborative reading.	3.41 AE
10	I find it challenging to maintain students' motivation and participation, particularly for those who are not used to collaborative learning.	3.23 AE
Composite Mean		2.83 UE
After Implementation		
11	I find it hard to assess individual student reading progress effectively within a collaborative reading.	2.23 SE
12	I lack sufficient time to conduct post-activity discussions due to tight schedules.	2.70 UE
13	I encountered students' resistance in collaborative reading.	2.18 SE
14	I find it challenging to provide differentiated support to students with varying reading abilities.	2.29 SE
15	I lack access to sufficient instructional materials tailored for collaborative reading activities	2.18 SE
Composite Mean		2.31 SE
General Composite Mean		2.50 UE

Table 4. Challenges Encountered by Junior High School Teachers Using Collaborative Reading Strategies

The table 4 presents the challenges encountered in the implementation of Collaborative Reading. Among the identified concerns, Indicator 9 "I encounter classroom management issues such as noise, and off-task behavior during collaborative reading," obtained a weighted mean of 3.41, verbally interpreted as Always Encountered (AE). This indicates that managing learner behavior and maintaining order during group activities is a consistent challenge for teachers. Similarly, Indicator 10, "I find it challenging to maintain students' motivation and participation, particularly for those who are not used to collaborative learning," received a weighted mean of 3.24 (AE). It shows that teachers frequently have difficulty in the classroom sustaining learners' interest and active involvement. On the other hand, Indicator 2, "I consume a lot of time crafting collaborative reading activities, especially when considering appropriate tasks for students with varying reading abilities," garnered a weighted mean of 3.00, interpreted as Usually Encountered (UE). It illustrates that time and preparation demands are significant concerns before conducting collaborative reading.

These findings indicate that the challenges in implementing collaborative reading strategies arise from three primary factors: (1) classroom management conditions, (2) learners' motivation and readiness, and (3) the time and effort required for instructional planning and preparation. The challenges in classroom management are largely influenced by large class sizes, varied learners' abilities, and group tasks that can lead to distractions when not closely monitored. Some learners may prefer individual work or may lack the social and communication skills necessary for effective group participation, which often results in unsuccessful or less productive group tasks. In addition, time constraints in preparing differentiated materials and structuring collaborative activities can hinder teachers from thoroughly planning lessons, providing individualized support, and consistently and effectively implementing collaborative reading strategies.

The three factors that arise from the findings were supported by Apiles (2025) as mentioned in the study: teachers struggle with time constraints, a dearth of diverse reading materials, and student disengagement, often leading them to simplify lessons and rely on repetitive practice. Additionally, Jumawid (2024) examined Grade 3 teachers in Davao City and found similar issues to those identified in the current study, including limited learner willingness, insufficient parental cooperation, and time constraints for diagnosing reading problems, selecting materials, and managing the classroom.

The study by Nguyen and Tran (2024) further highlighted a critical gap in the literature by exploring the classroom management challenges faced by novice EFL teachers in Vietnam, particularly in secondary school settings. Among the most persistent issues were a lack of concentration during grammar lessons and chatting during group activities, both of which significantly disrupted learning and increased teacher stress. Furthermore, Tippet & Bruno (2022) reported qualitative focus group findings indicating that self-efficacy in classroom management was strengthened by resources such as specialized training, clear rules and procedures, positive reinforcement, and ongoing parental support. Triangulated analysis indicated that teachers frequently used rewards and praise to manage disruptive behavior. The study suggests that providing dedicated time for teacher collaboration and offering targeted training in classroom practices can further enhance self-efficacy.

Indicators		Weighted Mean (WM)	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
Pre-implementation			
1	I prepare and gather appropriate reading materials ahead of time to support collaborative reading by selecting texts aligned with the lesson objectives, printing copies for each group, and including guiding questions, vocabulary lists, and graphic organizers to facilitate meaningful group discussions.	3.47	AT
2	I manage my time to craft collaborative reading strategies especially when considering the appropriate activities for different reading abilities of the students by preparing tiered reading materials and differentiated tasks in advance.	3.18	OT
3	I attend or request training sessions with my co-teachers to enhance my ability to support struggling readers.	2.94	OT
4	I adjust my lesson plans to align collaborative reading activities with curriculum standards.	3.41	AT
5	I develop motivational techniques to encourage low-level readers to join group activities.	3.53	AT
Composite Mean		3.30	AT
During Implementation			
6	I engage all learners in my class using visual aids and interactive activities, assigning peer buddies.	3.65	AT
7	I modify the pace or content of activities to fit the time limits of the subject by breaking longer reading passages into shorter sections	3.35	AT
8	I organize manageable group sizes and assign roles to reduce the effect of large class sizes.	3.35	AT
9	I implement behavior strategies to address off-task behavior during group work by setting clear expectations before the activity, positive reinforcement, and so on.	3.23	OT

10	I include motivating activities at all times (e.g., games, peer praise) to maintain student interest.	3.53	AT
Composite Mean		3.42	AT
After Implementation			
11	I use observation checklists or quick assessments to monitor individual reading progress.	3.53	AT
12	I allocate time for post-reading reflections or group sharing, even briefly.	3.41	AT
13	I speak individually with students who show resistance/ inconvenience to collaborative reading tasks.	3.47	AT
14	I provide localized/contextualized tasks or support depending on each student's reading level.	3.29	AT
15	I design or adapt instructional materials that are specific to collaborative reading sessions.	3.18	AT
Composite Mean		3.37	AT
General Composite Mean		3.36	AT

Table 9. Action-Taken by Junior High School Teachers to Address the Challenges

The table 9 presents the action taken by Junior High School teachers to address the challenges with a general composite mean of 3.36. Across all phases, Indicator 6 "I engage all learners in my class using visual aids and interactive activities, assigning peer buddies," with a weighted mean of 3.65 (Always Taken), is the most common action or solution of the teachers during collaborative reading. This suggests that teachers ensure every learner participates actively in reading tasks. During lessons, the frequent use of visual aids, collaborative activities, and varied instructional materials helps capture students' attention, maintain engagement, and support comprehension for diverse learning levels. This is followed by Indicator 5, "I develop motivational techniques to encourage low-level readers to join group activities," with a weighted mean of 3.53. The result indicates that teachers are aware of students who struggle with reading, prompting them to create encouraging and supportive classroom environments that promote participation. This action demonstrates the use of extrinsic motivation to inspire learners to engage in reading activities. Similarly, Indicator 11 "I use observation checklists or quick assessments to monitor individual reading progress," with a weighted mean of 3.53. It shows that teachers monitor individual reading progress to provide timely interventions and make instructional adjustments.

These findings reveal that teachers mainly address challenges on collaborative reading through engagement activities, extrinsic motivations, and continuous assessment. Thus, by doing so, teachers create effective support that promotes active participation and enhances reading outcomes for all learners.

The findings on engaging activities employed by teachers were reinforced by Manuas, Tatipang, and Pratasik (2022), who mentioned the importance of providing engaging reading and writing activities to build learners' enthusiasm for reading, noting that both male and female learners generally demonstrate similar levels of reading motivation. Similarly, Pangan et al. (2025) revealed that teachers often adapt through self-directed learning, technology integration, and learner-centered approaches despite facing limited materials and insufficient formal training. Moreover, the results of Tlonaen, Jaha, Ena, and Dewi (2025) demonstrated that collaborative and technology-supported strategies significantly enhanced engagement and performance among low-level readers. Also, Potot et al. (2023) found that using varied resources and tailoring tasks to individual and small-group needs significantly improves reading comprehension and learner motivation.

The findings on extrinsic motivation enforced by teachers align with the study by Manuas, Tatipang, and Pratasik (2022), which stated that teachers should provide engaging reading or writing activities to build learners' enthusiasm for reading. They also found that male and female students had similar perceptions, showing no significant difference in reading motivation. Motivational techniques, technology integration, and collaborative active learning significantly improved learners' learning outcomes and engagement, particularly among low-level readers, while the control group showed little to no change (Tlonaen, Jaha, Ena, & Dewi, 2025).

Meanwhile, findings from the continuous assessment indicate that the use of observation checklists and brief formative assessments enables teachers to monitor learners' progress. This is supported by the study of Luca and Afeez (2024), who emphasized that regular and systematic assessment provides educators with essential information about student progress, enabling timely and effective instructional adjustments.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that collaboreading strategies significantly enhance the learners' reading level in both sections in Grade 7. This reflects the positive impact of collaboreading strategies in enhancing learners' reading comprehension and ability to read independently. The result further revealed statistically significant results in the pre-assessment and post-assessment before and after using collaboreading strategies in class. This means the null hypothesis is rejected, stating that there is a significant difference in the results of pre-assessment and post-assessment.

The findings on the challenges encountered by Junior High School teachers revealed that they face challenges in classroom management, student motivation, and time preparation when using collaborative reading strategies in their classes. Despite that, they are proactive in addressing these challenges by engaging all learners through visual aids, interactive activities, peer-buddy systems, and monitoring individual reading progress through observation checklists and quick assessments.

Moreover, the proposed collaboreading framework proved to be an effective structured reading process to enhance the reading level of Grade 7 learners.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.